

Improvement of mechanical properties of impregnated resin for carbon fibre sheet by adding nano-silica

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Carbon fibre reinforced polymer (CFRP) has been identified as a promising solution for repairing metal bridges due to its high specific strength, non-damaging nature to steel substrates, and uniform stress distribution. However, epoxy resin, commonly used as a matrix material for manufacturing CFRP and as an adhesive in joints, faces challenges in coastal environments where high temperatures and humidity can lead to plasticisation, expansion, and hydrolysis, causing degradation of its mechanical properties. The study investigates nano-silica at varying proportions was used to modify the epoxy resin, followed by tensile tests. The results showed that as the nano-silica content increased, the tensile strength of the modified resin initially increased and then decreased. The tensile strength was maximized with a 2 wt% addition of nano-silica, yielding a 30% improvement. After deterioration of the neat and modified resin specimens in distilled water at 50°C for 60 days, the aged modified resin showed a remarkable enhancement in tensile strength compared to the aged neat resin, with an increase ranging from 39% to 52%.

1. Introduction

Epoxy resin (EPs) is recognized for its excellent mechanical properties and robust adhesive qualities, making it widely used as a matrix material for CFRP and as an adhesive in various industries, including civil engineering, automotive, and aerospace applications^[1-5]. In service, CFRP and adhesive joints are frequently subjected to extreme temperatures and humidity due to geographical and seasonal influences, which can result in a loss of mechanical properties of epoxy resin because the epoxy resin matrix is more sensitive to hygrothermal environments compared to the carbon fibre^[5-10].

Incorporating fillers into epoxy resin is a common approach to enhance its mechanical properties. Resin-based composite materials first appeared in the United States in 1932. Traditional polymer composite designs are based on the average effect, where modifications typically increase strength but often at the expense of toughness. This drawback arises from the properties of the dispersed phase, which is typically at the microscale and can easily become a stress concentration point within the polymer, resulting in premature material failure prior to achieving its ultimate mechanical performance. Nanomaterials (1-100 nm), with their exceptionally large surface area, can bond with the resin matrix to create more interfaces, thereby facilitating stress transfer and enhancing both the strength and toughness of the polymer^[1,11,12]. Additionally, several studies^[13,14] have shown that adding a small amount of nanomaterials can improve the thermal stability of epoxy resin.

Resin absorbs moisture through two distinct mechanisms: first, as free water that infiltrates the material's free space and initiates

plasticisation. The rate of diffusion is governed by the material's physical properties. The second mechanism involves 2 types of bound water. Type I bound water is manifested by disrupting the weaker inter-chain Van der Waals forces and acts as a plasticiser. Type II bound water is a product of strong hydrogen bonds between water molecules and the resin network. The amount of Type II bound water, which is more difficult to remove and causes irreversible material changes, increases with higher temperature and longer exposure time^[15]. This bonding leads to expansion and plasticisation, causing a reduction in both the strength and glass transition temperature (T_g) of the material. Therefore, to limit excessive infiltration of free water into epoxy resin and reduce the risk of irreversible damage from bound water, many researchers incorporate nanomaterials to modify the epoxy resin^[7,16]. Nanomaterials occupy fine voids within the epoxy resin and modify as well as extend the diffusion pathways of moisture, thereby diminishing the impact of moisture degradation on the resin performance^[17]. Bi^[18] researched through combined experimental and molecular dynamics approaches that nanoparticles capture water molecules by forming hydrogen bonds, restricting their mobility and reducing the water absorption rate in epoxy resin.

To evaluate the impact of nano-silica on the mechanical properties of epoxy resin under hygrothermal conditions. Epoxy resin samples modified with varying nano-silica proportions were prepared, immersed in distilled water for degradation, and subsequently subjected to tensile test in this paper.

2. Experimental programs

2.1 Materials

An epoxy resin and curing agent set named XL-800 was adopted, which was produced by Mitsubishi Chemical Infracore Co., Ltd. The epoxy resin is gel-like liquid, and the curing agent is thin liquid at room temperature. The epoxy resin is green in colour, and the curing agent is light orange. The weight mixing ratio of the resin and the curing agent is 4:1. The silane coupling agent (SCA) X-12-972F was supplied by Shin-Etsu Chemical Co., Ltd., the silane coupling agent features low volatility and contains more reactive functional groups with resin compared to monomeric types. Nano-silica QSG-30 was also manufactured in Shin-Etsu Chemical Co., Ltd, nano-silica is in the form of a white powder with a particle size of approximately 30 nm and specific surface area of 150 m²/g, all the materials are shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Materials: (a) Epoxy resin of XL-800, (b) Curing agent of XL-800, (c) Nano-silica particle QSG-30.

2.2 Specimen preparation

Nano-fillers can be incorporated into epoxy resin using two primary methods: When the epoxy resin has high fluidity, ultrasonic vibration alone is sufficient to effectively disperse nano materials within it. For lower fluidity adhesives, mechanical stirring is necessary. Due to the high viscosity of the epoxy resin used in this study, mechanical stirring and centrifugal defoaming were employed to achieve uniform dispersion of nano-silica within the resin. A silane coupling agent was utilized to improve nano-silica dispersion within the epoxy resin and to address the issue of limited interfacial bonding strength between them. Notably, excessive addition of the silane coupling agent significantly decreases the tensile strength of the epoxy resin. Thus, no more than 1 wt% of the silane coupling agent was incorporated. Table 1 presents the contents of nano-silica and SCA within the epoxy resin for each experimental condition, various proportions of nano-silica and silane coupling agent were incorporated into the epoxy resin and stirred mechanically at 2500 rpm for 1 hour to break up agglomerates of nano-particles as much as possible, the curing agent was then introduced into the thoroughly mixed epoxy resin, a centrifuge was operated at 2200 rpm for 10 minutes to degas the epoxy resin. The mixed resin was cast into a tensile specimen mould and subsequently placed in a temperature and humidity chamber at

35°C for 5 days in order to ensure that the epoxy resin had fully cured. The detailed preparation process is illustrated in Fig. 2.

Table 1 Specimen modification content and ageing condition

Specimen ID	Nano-silica content (wt%)	SCA content (wt%)	Duration (days)	Immersion temperature (°C)
Neat	0	0	/	/
M0.5	0.5	0.5	/	/
M1	1	1	/	/
M2	2	1	/	/
M4	4	1	/	/
Neat-60H	0	0	60	50
M0.5-60H	0.5	0.5	60	50
M1-60H	1	1	60	50
M2-60H	2	1	60	50
M4-60H	4	1	60	50

Note: M stands for nano-silica modified, and the number after M indicates its contents; H stands for hydrothermal condition, and the number before H indicates immersion period.

Fig. 2. Nano-silica modified epoxy resin preparation procedure.

2.3 Tensile test setup

The dimensions of the tensile specimens followed ISO 527-2 standard, with the test section measuring 60 mm × 10 mm × 4 mm, as shown in Fig. 3(a). Tensile tests were performed on a universal testing machine (Tokyo Koki Tester MSC-10/500-2) at a tensile loading rate of 5 mm/min, with a strain gauge attached to the centre of the test section to measure strain during testing, as shown in Fig. 3(b). The reason for choosing a higher loading speed is to eliminate resin viscosity effects^[11].

Following the high-temperature immersion ageing process, the test specimens were placed in a drying oven (10% RH) for 7 days to remove surface moisture and eliminate free water and part of Type I bond water. The edges of the test section were polished with sandpaper to prevent stress concentration caused by protrusions, which could lead to premature failure of the specimen. All tests were conducted three times.

2.4 High-temperature immersion test setup

In order to evaluate the impact of nano-silica modification on

the mechanical performance of epoxy resin in highly humid and elevated temperatures, a high-temperature immersion test was devised. In many regions, surface temperatures can reach 50°C during the summer months, while previous studies indicate the epoxy resin used in this study has a glass transition temperature of 60°C^[19]. In engineering applications, epoxy resin temperature limits are typically set at 10°C below T_g . Thus, specimens were immersed in distilled water at 50°C for 60 days to simulate extremely humid and high-temperature conditions, as illustrated in Fig. 4.

(a) Specimen dimension

(b) Tensile test setup

Fig. 3. Specimen dimension and tensile test setup.

Fig. 4. Deterioration test setup for specimens immersed in distilled water at 50°C.

2.5 SEM microscopic analysis

The tensile test specimens were cut to a size appropriate for placement in the scanning electron microscope (SEM) chamber. The dried sample was then affixed to the loading stage with conductive adhesive tape in order to ensure its stability. The sample underwent osmium coating in a vacuum environment to enhance its conductivity, thereby improving the clarity of SEM images at higher magnifications. Subsequently, the fracture surface of the tensile test specimen was observed and analyzed using SEM (Hitachi SU8000) with an accelerating voltage of 2 kV under vacuum conditions.

3. Experimental results and analysis

3.1 Mechanical properties of neat and modified epoxy resin

The mechanical properties of the epoxy resin with varying nano-silica contents were determined, including tensile strengths and elastic modulus, as plotted in Fig. 5(a), and the stress-strain curve is shown in Fig. 5(b). The elastic modulus was determined in accordance with ISO 527-1 by means of a linear fit to the stress-strain data in the strain range of 0.05% to 0.25%.

As illustrated in Fig. 5(a), the tensile strength of epoxy resin initially increases with the addition of nano-silica but subsequently decreases with further increases in content. This behaviour occurs because nano-silica is well-dispersed at low contents, while excessive nano-silica results in agglomeration, causing stress concentrations at agglomerate sites during tensile testing, which leads to premature specimen fracture. With a nano-silica content of 2 wt% in the epoxy resin, the tensile strength increased by 30% compared to neat epoxy resin.

The elastic modulus of modified epoxy resin changes with varying nano-silica contents. As the nano-silica content increased from 0 wt% to 1 wt%, the elastic modulus of the epoxy resin increased by 16%. However, with further increases in nano-silica content, the elastic modulus of epoxy resin decreases.

(a) Tensile strength and elastic modulus of neat and modified epoxy resin

(b) Stress-strain curve of neat and modified epoxy resin

Fig. 5. Mechanical properties of epoxy resin with various nano-silica contents.

The coefficient of variation (CV) was introduced to assess the dispersion of sample data, facilitating comparisons between different data groups. The expression is presented in Eq. (1).

$$CV = \frac{S}{\bar{X}} \times 100\% \quad (1)$$

where S represents the standard deviation of the experimental samples, and \bar{X} represents the mean value of the experimental samples.

Potential defects during specimen preparation may cause the sample to suddenly fail upon reaching, or even before reaching, the yield strength during tensile testing, as shown in Fig. 5(b). The maximum fracture displacement (D_{max}) is also used as a reference for assessing material toughness. The maximum fracture displacement of all nano-silica modified epoxy resin exceeds that of the neat epoxy resin, as shown in Table 2. The relationship between maximum fracture displacement and nano-silica content parallels that of the elastic modulus and nano-silica content. It is noteworthy that when the proportion of nanoparticles is 1wt%, the maximum fracture displacement reaches its peak, exhibiting an increase of 17% in comparison to the neat epoxy resin.

Conversely, the trend in average fracture displacement with nano-silica content between 0 wt% and 4 wt% is not significant. With nano-silica contents at 1 wt% and 2 wt%, the average fracture displacement increased by 13% and 23%, respectively, compared to neat epoxy resin; however, at 0.5 wt% and 4 wt% nano-silica content, the fracture displacement decreased by 8% and 15%, respectively. The premature failure of epoxy resin modified with 4 wt% nano-silica is related to the tendency of nano-silica to agglomerate at high contents. The agglomeration of nanoparticles at high contents is clearly visible in Fig. 6(c). This occurs due to the strong Van der Waals forces between nanoparticles, which promote particle attraction. At low proportions, the shear forces generated by mechanical stirring can disperse adjacent nanoparticles, however, at higher proportions, the effectiveness of mechanical stirring in dispersing nanoparticles is significantly reduced. This result is consistent with findings from other studies^[20,21]. As for the epoxy resin modified with 0.5 wt% nano-silica, its average fracture displacement is lower than that of the neat epoxy resin, which is believed to be related to preparation defects. During fabrication, the epoxy resin was not uniformly cast into the mould, and due to its poor flowability, air trapped in the areas of the mould was not covered by the resin, resulting in small bubbles in this batch of specimens.

Table 2 Fracture displacement of neat and modified epoxy resin.

Specimen ID	Fracture displacement		
	D_{max} (mm)	Average (mm)	CV (%)
Neat	3.48	3.15	13.08
M0.5	3.58	2.78	20.24
M1	4.08	3.56	21.34
M2	3.99	3.86	3.26
M4	3.60	2.56	28.63
Neat-60H	2.49	2.36	6.82
M0.5-60H	4.05	3.61	12.19
M1-60H	5.11	3.93	26.11
M2-60H	4.34	3.23	31.52
M4-60H	3.86	3.40	11.85

Fig. 6. SEM image of tensile fracture surface of epoxy resin.

The SEM image of the tensile fracture surface of epoxy resin is presented in Fig. 6. The tensile fracture surface of neat resin appears smooth with some slight protrusions or wrinkles. Upon the addition of nano-silica, the roughness of the specimen's tensile fracture surface significantly increases, accompanied by the emergence of wrinkles, distributed more extensively. In the SEM images of the tensile fracture surface of nano-silica modified epoxy resin, nano-silica particles could be observed clearly. The zigzag cracks in the diamond-marked region are believed to result from nano-silica altering the crack propagation direction during tension, thereby lengthening the crack path and enhancing material strength and toughness. The protrusions and wrinkles (marked with ellipses) indicate areas where the resin uses nano-silica as a stress concentration point under tensile load, leading to localised plastic deformation that absorbs fracture energy.

3.2 Hygrothermal effect on mechanical properties

Fig. 7(a) shows the tensile strength and elastic modulus of the neat epoxy resin and modified epoxy resins after 60 days of immersion ageing at 50°C, while Fig. 7(b) presents the stress-strain curves for the aged epoxy resins. The values on the bar chart indicate the improvement in tensile strength for each modified epoxy resin compared to the aged neat epoxy resin.

(a) Tensile strength and elastic modulus of neat and modified epoxy resin after ageing

(b) Stress-strain curve of neat and modified epoxy resin after ageing

Fig. 7. Mechanical properties of epoxy resin after ageing with various nano-silica contents.

Fig. 7(a) clearly shows that immersion at 50°C for 60 days results in a significant 29% reduction in the tensile strength of neat epoxy resin. In contrast, strength reduction is less pronounced in nano-filler reinforced epoxy resins, with epoxy resin containing 0.5 wt%, 1 wt%, 2 wt%, and 4 wt% nano-silica showing reductions of 8%, 10%, 24%, and 6%, respectively. This indicates that increasing nano-filler content effectively enhances the strength of aged epoxy resin. This enhancement can be attributed to nano-fillers occupying original micro voids, making it more difficult for water to penetrate the resin within the same time frame, thereby mitigating the negative effects of hygrothermal ageing.

According to the fracture displacement data in Table 2, neat epoxy resin becomes more brittle after hygrothermal ageing, with a 25% reduction in average fracture displacement. In contrast, the average fracture displacements under tensile load for M0.5, M1, and M4 specimens show significant increases of 10%, 30%, and 33%, respectively, following hygrothermal ageing compared to their unaged counterparts. This indicates that epoxy resin modified with nano-silica becomes tougher after hygrothermal ageing. Comparison of the CV in Table 3 reveals that M2-60H exhibits a high variability in tensile load, along with the highest CV in fracture displacement among different sample groups, this suggests that certain M2-60H specimens failed before reaching their ultimate load capacity during tensile testing, likely due to defects introduced during resin moulding.

Table 3 Ultimate force of neat and modified epoxy resin.

Specimen ID	Ultimate force		
	F_{max} (N)	Average (N)	CV (%)
Neat	1830	1750	3.97
M0.5	2105	2038.33	2.93
M1	2190	2106.67	5.85
M2	2295	2271.67	1.59
M4	2085	1933.33	5.71
Neat-60H	1305	1295	4.57
M0.5-60H	1895	1875	1.97
M1-60H	1960	1891.67	2.42
M2-60H	1930	1745	10.75
M4-60H	1810	1796.67	1.05

3.3 Discussion

Based on the above tensile test results and SEM images of the modified resin fracture surface, it can be inferred that the primary mechanisms by which nano-silica enhances and toughens epoxy resin under tensile loading are crack pinning and crack path deflection. A schematic of the toughening mechanisms is shown in Fig. 8.

In hygrothermal environments, the interaction between water molecules and polar groups in the resin significantly weakens its mechanical properties. Higher temperatures intensify resin relaxation, thereby increasing diffusion pathways for water molecules. Adding an appropriate amount of nano-silica significantly enhances the mechanical performance of epoxy resin after hygrothermal ageing, primarily because nano-silica obstructs the diffusion channels of water molecules within the resin.

Fig. 8. Schematic representation of enhancement mechanisms of nano-silica modified resin: ① crack propagation deflection, ② crack pinning.

4. Conclusions

- (1) Suitable proportions of nano-silica can improve the mechanical properties of epoxy resin.
- (2) Nano-silica can significantly mitigate the impact of hygrothermal environments on the degradation of the mechanical properties of epoxy resin.
- (3) The primary mechanisms by which nano-fillers toughen and reinforce epoxy resin are crack pinning and crack propagation deflection.

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